

RECOMMENDATIONS ON DEVELOPING LITERARY PRONUNCIATION SKILLS IN MOTHER LANGUAGE CLASSES

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Abstract. Improving the content of educational materials related to orthography in the educational system, increasing orthographic literacy is one of the urgent issues today. The basis of any language is its sound system, that is, phonetics and orthography. In the scientific literature on the teaching of other developed foreign languages, special attention is paid to pronunciation and orthoepic exercises are effectively used in the educational process. In this article, theoretical information and a number of practical recommendations on the development of correct, fluent, expressive speech in students, as well as the phonetic phenomena that form the basis of the rules of orthography, have been touched upon.

Key words : phonetics, orthography, pronunciation, dialect, assimilation, dissimilation, spirantization, metathesis, prosthesis, epenthesis, dieresis, elision, epithesis, syncope.

each field has aspects that distinguish it from other fields, literary pronunciation also has certain laws that ensure its independence. These regularities consist of a set of traditional regularities that have passed through various tests over the centuries, and at the same time, new speech (pronunciation) phenomena that have just appeared. One of the difficulties in solving this problem is the issue of dialects. It is known that the Uzbek language has four dialects and many dialects. Each of these dialects and dialects has its own phonetic and articulatory features, and in this respect they differ from each other. If the Kipchak dialects are characterized by the pronunciation of the consonant **q** instead of the consonant **x** (such as *qat, qatin, qalq*), the phenomenon of pronouncing **k** instead of **q** can be observed in some of the dialects of the Karluq-Chigil group: *kant, kamchi, kayerga* (written like *sugar, whip, where*). necessary to make a brief comment on some phonetic phenomena. Because these phenomena are actually phonetic phenomena that form the basis of orthographic rules. Among such important phonetic phenomena, the following can be included:

Assimilation. Phonetic phenomena that occur as a result of one sound affecting a neighboring sound are called assimilation. Depending on the character of the change of the affected sound, assimilation is divided into the following types:

- one consonant affects another consonant and makes it completely similar to itself: like *seven - seven, horse - horse, without salt - without color*. This type of assimilation is called complete assimilation;
- a sound affects a neighboring sound, not completely simulating it, but changes only one side of it (turns it into an unvoiced consonant or a voiced consonant). And this is called incomplete assimilation: *gegen - ketkan, oshdan - oshtan, koshdi - koshti*.

Dissimilation. Dissimilation is the movement of a sound from its position in a word. This type of phonetic change is more common, especially in the language of children and speech-impaired people. *Damage - zalal, corridor - kalidor, necessary - zaril, one - one.*

Spirantization. The basic meaning of this phenomenon is that the original explosive sound in the word turns into a sliding consonant, and as a result there is a difference between pronunciation and writing. For example: *praise - praise, doctor - doctor.*

Metathesis. This means the exchange of some sounds in the word. For example: *soil - root, curse - curse, supra - surpa.*

Prosthesis. It is the addition of a vowel sound to a word during speech. For example; *glass - istakan, table - ustol, Russian - Russian.*

Epenthesis. It is a phenomenon where some vowel sounds are joined between two consonants without the written form of the word. For example: *mind - mind, lion - lion, bed - bed.*

Diereza. It is said that certain sounds in the word are pronounced by omitting them. For example: *pas - pas, rost - ros, Tashkent - Toshkan*

Elysia. Two words **As a result of the collision of the vowels** on the edge, one of those vowels is dropped. For example: *could not go - could not go, could not write - could not write, parents - father.*

Epithesis. It is said that a vowel is added at the end of the word. For example: *bank - bank, kiosk - kiosk.*

Syncope. It refers to the phenomenon of dropping some vowel sounds between two and polysyllabic words. For example: *clothes - clothes, grapes - grapes, children - children [1].*

In addition, hyphenated words are always added and pronounced as a whole. For example: *food, child, honor, entertainment, fruit, fruit, etc.*

Teaching students to pronounce words correctly is carried out in 3 stages:

Step 1. Forming the pronunciation of certain sounds involves working on the pronunciation of hard and soft, voiced and unvoiced consonants;

B -lab, explosive, sonorous consonant. It comes at the end, beginning and middle of the word. For example, *b obo, ta b iat, ajoyi b*

B- pronounced like **V**; *aro b a-ara v a, ka b ob-ka v ob.*

P -lab, explosive, voiceless consonant. For example, *p iyola, di p lom, tur p*

B and **F** are pronounced instead of consonants. For example, *f abrika - p abrika, keli b - keli p.*

Stage 2. Forming the pronunciation of certain words is the correct pronunciation of the lexicon, accentuation, separation of the stressed syllable in the word;

Lexically: "Koklam came" one means the name of the season, the other means the action. The accent falls on the last syllable of the word: *Tailor, ti-kuv-chi.*

Stage 3: Forming the pronunciation of sample sentences - this involves special work on the tones of specific sentences. A sparrow is a small bird [2].

Paronyms are formed as a result of violations of orthographic rules. Paronyms are words that are similar in pronunciation, but have different spellings and meanings. For example, *abzal - afzal, kuyulmak - kuyulmak, daha - daho, bob - bop, ahl - ahil, asr - asir, azm - azim, darz - dars, kayt - kayt, yod - yot, very - judo, yondosh - approach, etc.*

it is necessary to explain to the students that two different spellings of the same word are not paronyms . For example, *king - king, grandson - grandson, beggar - gado* . Such words are doublets , and it is not a mistake to use either of them in text or speech.

The phenomenon of simple speech in the Uzbek language is another obstacle in the work of determining the pronunciation norm. For example: *there - seven, five; here - botta, betta; to this side - back; to this side - shagga*, also *ettan, bettan, shettan, Uzbek (Uzbek); such as moshin, journal, and belat* belong to the phenomenon of simple speech. The correct solution of the relationship of the above non-literary speech phenomena to the literary standard, listed in oral speech, occupies an important place in the work of improving the skills of speech culture [3].

the words *book, mirage, free, generation, raisin, mint* and similar words are pronounced. When determining the correct pronunciation of such words, it can be determined by placing the corresponding vowel on the final consonant . For example: *free (t) + neat, mirage (p) + mirage, mint (s) + mint*.

Many errors in both pronunciation and spelling by students are related to the incorrect use of the throat consonants " **h**" and " **x**" **in the word structure** . Here are some ways to solve the problems associated with using these sounds.

1. *Pronounce the first sound several times (focus on the production of the sound).*

hhhhhh

xxxxxxxx

2. *Pronounce the given words correctly (pay attention to the explanation).*

both (and conjunction)

raw (oblique)

all (all, total)

hamma (wheat container)

hil (steam)

type

king (king)

branch (branch)

situation

score (body mark)

hush (res, mind)

good (great)[4]

literary pronunciation skills , it is advisable to develop a system of exercises based on the recommendations given below.

1. In the first syllable of lexemes such as " *heart*" and " *wood*" , the next syllable of lexemes with the sound of "o" is pronounced not -u, but -i.

of the lexeme has the sound -o, then the next closed syllable that starts with the sound -v is pronounced -u instead of -i: *soap, sound, saxophone*.

3. If the first syllable of the lexeme has the sound -u, then the next closed syllable is pronounced -u instead of -i: *star, achievement, life, node*

4. *duk -duk, gov-guv* image units such as *dukur-dukur, govur-guvur*, the sound -u is pronounced before the sound -r.

5. In Arabic lexemes such as *تينا, لى, ميرا, يتيكود*, the sound before the stop sign is pronounced with a lengthening.[5]

In conclusion, the correct pronunciation of words is one of the important signs of speech culture. Correct pronunciation is as important as correct writing in literary language. That's why it is necessary to pay serious attention to the formation of correct pronunciation skills in students at all stages of education.

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